

Wavelength Based Information/Entropy, Lorentz Transformations and Refraction

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In a previous note (1) we argued that there should be a quantum entropy based on wavelength as there is uncertainty within this length region. In other words a free quantum particle should have a wavelength dependent entropy while the traditional $S = - \int dx W^*(x)W(x) \ln\{W^*(x)W(x)\}$ ((1)) yields $W^*(x)W(x) = \exp(-ipx) \exp(ipx) / \text{length} = 1/\text{length}$ for all wavelengths. If a single, double etc slit experiment is performed, a pattern of crests and troughs is observed and entropy is calculated using ((1)). This entropy depends on the wavelength as well as the number of slits so we argue that a free particle carries entropy based on its wavelength.

In (1) it was noted that a photon (which has a wavelength) may refract in various media and change its wavelength. If entropy is wavelength dependent then it appears that there are spontaneous increases or decreases in this entropy (depending on whether the wavelength increases or decreases). It is not only refraction, however, that leads to changes in wavelength, but Lorentz transformations as well. In fact, both refraction and Lorentz transformations may be shown to be linked to Fermat's minimum time principle (2).

In this note we argue that even though wavelengths may change due to Lorentz transformations or changes of media, one may consider the idea of a local entropy restricted to one particular media or reference frame. For example, a change in the speed of light in a medium may account for the change in wavelength. For a person in the particular medium all wavelengths change or scale so one need not necessarily compare the wavelength in the two media when considering the information in one medium. In other words information or entropy may be medium/frame dependent.

Possible Reason for Wavelength Based Entropy

As noted above, Shannon's entropy is traditionally applied to $P(x) = W^*(x)W(x)$ (3) where $W(x)$ is the wavelength. This implies that such an entropy is a constant for a free particle with $W(x) = \exp(ipx) / \sqrt{L}$ where L is length. We argued in (1) that this result applies to the uniform center of mass motion of a free particle i.e. $v = x/t = \text{constant}$. The form $\exp(ipx)$ is consistent with this uniform motion, i.e. is two dimensional ($\cos(px)$, $\sin(px)$). We have argued before that this represents two shifted sets of probability distributions needed to describe uniform motion and its direction in space. We argue, however, that this does not change the intrinsic uncertainty within a wavelength. Furthermore we argue that entropy calculations using ((1)) are applied to patterns emerging from a free particle/photon passing through a single slit, two slits, three slits etc. Each of these patterns is different depending on the number of slits, but the result also depends on the wavelength (e.g. textbook equations of $d \sin(\theta) = n \text{ wavelength}$ etc). In other words the wavelength is an important part of the pattern and hence the entropy result and we argue that by consistency the free particle should carry an entropy/information (uncertainty) due to its wavelength.

We also note that a wavelength is related to information as it describes the resolution of space. In other words a small wavelength allows one to resolve more details and obtain more information than a large one. Information is traditionally linked to entropy in Shannon's picture. Wavelength, however, may change due to Lorentz transformations or refraction, seemingly leading to a change in information. We try to examine these issues in the next sections.

Lorentz Transformations

If one has a wavelength based entropy, what happens when Lorentz transformations occur? In quantum mechanics $p = \hbar / \text{wavelength}$ for both a photon and particle with rest mass. In one frame (considered to be at rest) there is a p (momentum), wavelength ($p = \hbar / \text{wavelength}$ and $E = pc$) and resolution length equal to the wavelength. One may create a ruler of exactly this length. In a moving frame there is a p' and wavelength' such that $E' = p'c$. The ruler in the rest frame contracts in the moving frame as seen by the observer in the rest frame $L' = L \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$, but this length is no longer the wavelength in the moving frame as seen by the rest one. The Lorentz transformation with $E = pc$ yields:

$$P' = \gamma p - \gamma v g \quad \text{where } g = \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2} \quad c=1 \quad ((2)) \quad \text{so } p' = \gamma p (1 - v) \quad \text{and } p' = \hbar / \text{wavelength}'$$

Thus light which keeps its speed c as viewed from both frames has a different momentum linked to a different wavelength. An entropy calculated using wavelength would then differ in the two frames. If entropy, however, is a measure of average information it is as if information is somehow lost or gained which seems unusual. It is, however, not unusual if one restricts oneself to the notion of entropy or information in a particular frame.

Refraction

Refraction also leads to changes in wavelength i.e. $p_i = \hbar n_i / \text{wavelength}(\text{vacuum})$ where n_i is the index of refraction of medium i . If one creates a wavelength based entropy then this seems to spontaneously change in each medium. If the wavelength being small implies low entropy (and vice versa) one may have entropy increase or decrease spontaneously depending on the medium, violating the second law of thermodynamics. If the wavelength represents information i.e. resolution of space, then it seems information is lost or gained spontaneously which appears unusual.

In order to analyze this situation, one may note that even though $p_i = \hbar n_i / \text{wavelength}(\text{vacuum})$ one may have any $\text{wavelength}(\text{vacuum})$ value and so each of these scales in the same way. Thus there is a consistency in the new medium. One simply needs to focus on entropy in each medium separately without having a global observer comparing the wavelength in each medium. One also has to note that wavelength is not the only piece of information present There is also the speed of light which is c/n_i . Thus for $n_i > 1$, the speed of light is less than that in a vacuum. In particular $E = pc$ and $p n_i c/n_i = E$. Thus E , energy, is the same in all media. In other words there are two pieces of information and their product does not change even though the "information" of each changes. In (4) it is suggested that e/kT (i.e. energy over temperature) is proportional to the information= entropy of an object with kinetic

energy e . In that case, information would not change in the various media during refraction. We, however, would like to keep a wavelength based entropy because it is linked to interactions with slits etc and interference in bound states.

In the case of refraction, one may see that:

$$d_i = \frac{c}{n_i} \text{ to } d = c \text{ to } \quad (3)$$

Given that clocks don't change in different media, d_i and d differ in exactly a way as to describe the differences in momentum or wavelength. Thus the so-called loss or gain of information due to the change in wavelength is due to the change in the speed of light. If light speed in a particular medium is used as a standard, then information in different media is not lost or gained. It just has to be considered to be a value linked to the speed of light in that medium. As a result, we argue that a wavelength based entropy should be considered separately in local media or frames.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue as in (1) that a wavelength based entropy should exist for a free particle. Using $P(x) = W^*(x)W(x)$ in Shannon's entropy formula as typically done (3) leads to a constant entropy for all wavelengths, but single, double, triple slit etc experiments produce wavelength dependent results and entropy calculations are made based on these patterns. Thus we argue there is an intrinsic wavelength based entropy. Wavelengths, however, may change such as in a Lorentz transformation or refraction. We argue that in both cases, one may consider this wavelength based entropy as frame/medium specific. In the case of refraction not only does the wavelength change, but the speed of light as well. As a result, all wavelengths scale the same way in a medium and there is really not a change relative to the speed of light in that medium i.e. $d = \frac{c}{n_i}$ to. Thus in the case of wavelength based entropy one has to be careful about considering spontaneous changes in entropy because in some cases the wavelength changes, but this only gives the appearance of a loss of information if one takes a global view and examines the wavelengths in different media together and ignores the fact that the speed of light is also changing

References

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